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APPLICATION OF FRACTIONAL-ORDER LEGENDRE FUNCTIONS FOR SOLVING FRACTIONAL DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we use the fractional-order Legendre functions to obtain a numerical solution for fractional differential equations (FDEs). The main idea of this study is based on the integral and fractional derivative operational matrices of fractional-order Legendre functions. Numerical results are included to demonstrate the efficiency of the present technique.

Key words and phrases: Fractional-order Legendre functions; Operational matrix of fractional derivative; Operational matrix of integration.
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1. INTRODUCTION

Fractional differential equations are generalizations of the ordinary differential equations to an arbitrary order. FDEs have attracted considerable interest due to their ability to model complex phenomena [3]. In this paper, we develop a new approximation method using fractional-order Legendre functions and their applications for solving FDEs.

2. PRELIMINARIES

We give some basic concepts of the fractional calculus theory, which are used further in [3].

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Definition 2.1. The fractional derivative of order ν in the Caputo sense for $m \in \mathbb{N}$ where $m - 1 < \nu \leq m$ and $x > 0$ is defined as:

$$D^\nu f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(m - \nu)} \int_0^x (x - t)^{m - \nu - 1} f^{(m)}(t) dt.$$

For the Caputo derivative we have:

$$D^\nu x^\gamma = \begin{cases} 0, & \gamma \in \mathbb{N}_0 \text{ and } \gamma < \nu, \\ \frac{\Gamma(\gamma + 1)}{\Gamma(\gamma + 1 - \nu)} x^{\gamma - \nu}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

3. FRACTIONAL-ORDER LEGENDRE FUNCTIONS

To solve FDEs, we employ the fractional-order Legendre functions, which are defined with the weight function $w(x) = x^{\alpha - 1}$ in the interval $[0, 1]$ [3]:

$$P_0^\alpha(x) = 1, \quad P_1^\alpha(x) = 2x^\alpha - 1,$$

$$(3.1) \quad P_{m+1}^\alpha(x) = \frac{(2m+1)(2x^\alpha - 1)}{m+1} P_m^\alpha(x) - \frac{m}{m+1} P_{m-1}^\alpha(x), \quad m = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

4. FUNCTION APPROXIMATION

A function $f(x)$ defined over $[0, 1]$ may be expressed in terms of fractional-order Legendre functions as:

$$f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} b_i P_i^\alpha(x),$$

where the coefficients b_i are given by,

$$(4.1) \quad b_i = \alpha(2i + 1) \int_0^1 P_i^\alpha(x) f(x) w(x) dx, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots$$

Therefore, one can consider the following truncated series for f :

$$(4.2) \quad f(x) \simeq \sum_{i=0}^M b_i P_i^\alpha(x) = B^T P_\alpha(x),$$

where $B = [b_0, b_1, \dots, b_M]^T$, $P_\alpha(x) = [P_0^\alpha(x), P_1^\alpha(x), \dots, P_M^\alpha(x)]^T$.

5. OPERATIONAL MATRIX OF INTEGRATION

To calculate integral operational matrix of the fractional-order Legendre functions, we have,

$$\int_0^x P_\alpha(\xi) d\xi \simeq \psi P_\alpha(x),$$

where ψ is the operational matrix of integration with $(M + 1) \times (M + 1)$ order that is obtained from the integration of the elements of the vector $P_\alpha(x)$.

6. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND NUMERICAL METHOD

Here, we focus on the following FDEs:

$$(6.1) \quad \begin{cases} D^2 y(x) + D^\nu y(x) + y(x) = f(x), & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \quad 0 < \nu < 2, \\ y(0) = y_0, \quad y'(0) = y'_0, \end{cases}$$

where $f(x)$ is known function and y_0, y'_0 are known values. In this section, we use the fractional-order Legendre functions for solving considered problem. First, we expand $D^2 y(x)$:

$$(6.2) \quad D^2 y(x) \simeq A^T P_\alpha(x),$$

by using equations (4.2) and (6.2), we have:

$$(6.3) \quad f(x) \simeq B^T P_\alpha(x),$$

$$(6.4) \quad y(x) \simeq A^T \psi^2 P_\alpha(x) + y'_0 x + y_0 = A^T \psi^2 P_\alpha(x) + g(x),$$

where $g(x) = y'_0 x + y_0$ and by using equation (4.2), we have:

$$(6.5) \quad D^\nu y(x) \simeq D^\nu (A^T \psi^2 P_\alpha(x) + C^T P_\alpha(x)) = (A^T \psi^2 + C^T) D^\nu P_\alpha(x),$$

also we have:

$$(6.6) \quad D^\nu P_\alpha(x) \simeq \eta P_\alpha(x),$$

where η is the operational matrix of fractional derivative for the fractional-order Legendre functions with $(M+1) \times (M+1)$ order. Finally, by substituting equations (6.2), (6.3), (6.4), (6.5) and (6.6) into equation (6.1) and removing $P_\alpha(x)$ from both sides of the achieved equation, we obtain the linear equations system that we can solve it easily. Then, we get the vector A and by substituting in equation (6.4), we obtain $y(x)$.

7. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

Example 7.1. Consider the following Bagley-Torvik equation with the initial conditions:

$$\begin{cases} D^2 y(x) + D^{\frac{3}{2}} y(x) + y(x) = f(x), \\ y(0) = y'(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

when $f(x) = \frac{15}{4}\sqrt{x} + \frac{15}{8}\sqrt{\pi}x + x^2\sqrt{x}$ [4], the approximation solution for $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ and $M = 5$ is $y(x) = x^2\sqrt{x}$, which is the exact solution of this equation. Also when $f(x) = 8$ [2], we compare our results for $M = 10$ and $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ with the Adomian method and Taylor matrix method [2] in table 1.

Example 7.2. Consider the following fractional differential equation with the initial conditions [1]:

$$\begin{cases} D^2 y(x) + D^{\frac{3}{4}} y(x) + y(x) = x^3 + 6x + \frac{128}{15\Gamma(\frac{1}{4})} x^{\frac{9}{4}}, & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y'(0) = 0, \end{cases}$$

the exact solution is $y(x) = x^3$. The approximation solution for $M = 6$ and $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$ is exact solution of this problem.

TABLE 1. Comparison of numerical results for Example 7.1 with $f(x) = 8$.

x	Exact solution	Adomian method [2]	Taylor method [2] M=16	Our method M=10
0	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
0.2	0.125221	0.140640	0.125254	0.125221
0.4	0.455435	0.533284	0.455468	0.455435
0.6	0.950392	1.148840	0.950398	0.950392
0.8	1.579557	1.963033	1.579689	1.579557
1	2.315526	2.952567	2.315589	2.315525

Example 7.3. Consider the following FDEs with the initial conditions:

$$\begin{cases} D^2 y(x) + D^\nu y(x) + y(x) = f(x), & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y'(0) = 1, \end{cases}$$

when $f(x) = 1 + x$ [2] with $\nu = \frac{3}{2}$, $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$, $M = 2$ the approximation solution is $y(x) = 1 + x$, which is the exact solution of this equation. Our method ($M = 2$) is more efficient than method of [2] ($M = 6$). For $f(x) = \frac{\sqrt{x}}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} + 1 + x$, $\nu = \frac{1}{2}$, exact solution is $y(x) = 1 + x$ which is obtained with $M = 2$ and $\alpha = \frac{1}{2}$.

Example 7.4. Consider the following FDEs with the initial conditions:

$$\begin{cases} D^2 y(x) + D^\nu y(x) - 2y(x) = 0, & 0 \leq x \leq 1, \\ y(0) = y'(0) = 1, \end{cases}$$

the exact solution, when $\nu = 1$ is $y(x) = e^x$. Figure 1 displays the absolute errors obtained between the approximation and exact solution in $\alpha = 1$ and different values of M .

FIGURE 1. Absolute errors obtained between the approximate solution and the exact solution with $\alpha = 1$.

8. CONCLUSION

The aim of the present work is to develop an efficient and accurate method for solving FDEs. We proposed integral and fractional derivative operational matrices for the considered problems, and utilizing them, we designed a numerical method.

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